

A Cross-Modal Approach to Shape Reconstruction of Deformable Linear Objects

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Abstract—This research focuses on applying cross-modal perception to reconstruct the shape of cables, which are treated as DLO (Deformable Linear Objects). The adoption of multiple sensing modalities –visual and tactile in this work– is crucial in those situations where the cable is only partially visible due to occlusions or camera faults. The challenge is twofold: finding a common representation for the two sensing data to obtain a single DLO model, e.g., a spline, and allowing the robot to explore the cable by autonomously deciding the sensing modality to adopt. The method is experimentally tested on a robot manipulator equipped with an RGB-D camera and a tactile sensor to reconstruct the cable shape from simple straight lines to more complex shapes, e.g., spiral-like shapes.

Index Terms—robotic manipulation, deformable linear object, cross-modal visuo-tactile sensing

I. INTRODUCTION

The problem of shape reconstruction of DLO's (in this work, cables) is a crucial building block of any robotic solution for the manipulation of challenging objects such as deformable objects. The growing interest of the robotics community in this topic is confirmed by the increasing number of papers devoted to it, such as [1], [2] and references therein. DLO manipulation is a common task in the manufacturing industry, where, e.g., wiring harness assembly [3] or switchgear cabling [4] are tasks difficult to automate. The challenges are mainly related to the difficulty of predicting the behaviour of the deformable object subject to the external forces necessary to manipulate it, mainly due to elasticity and plasticity phenomena. Moreover, real applications may need multiple cables (see Fig. 1), which could be easily entangled.

II. RELATED WORK

Regarding perception of DLO and their shape reconstruction, most of the existing works adopt visual perception. For example, [5] uses visual information to reconstruct the global shape of DLOs. Whereas, an interesting case study is presented in [6] where the shape estimation is performed by exploiting multiple 2D views. In particular, the work presents a pipeline that initially processes the image coming from 2D views and subsequently extracts the key topological points along the DLOs, which are used to model the objects through a B-spline curve. On the other hand, tactile sensors are, instead, used to infer the pose and local shape of the cable once it is grasped,

Fig. 1. Typical scenario of cable routing in the aerospace industry.

e.g., [4], [7]. The work in [8], instead, proposes a trained network on labelled point clouds (PC) acquired from a vision sensor and tested with an active tactile perception strategy. The aim is to recognize objects that have never been seen before to maximize the matching between the tactile and visual point clouds. In any case, none of the existing works deals with severe occlusions that might happen in a manufacturing scenario or even more frequently in an everyday environment due to the presence of other objects that might be intentionally or accidentally placed on the cable to be perceived, e.g., pieces of fabric, sheets of paper.

Therefore, this work aims to present preliminary results of a cross-modal perception algorithm where the shape of a single cable is reconstructed by resorting to both visual and tactile sensors under a few simplifying assumptions: the cable is not entangled, it has a uniform colour different from that of the background, the occluding object is soft enough to let the tactile sensor feel the presence of the cable below.

III. METHODOLOGY

The approach proposed here to reconstruct the shape of a DLO is based on cross-modal perception. This term refers to the adaptive, synergistic synthesis of complex perceptions from multiple sensory modalities, such that the perception that occurs within any individual sensory modality can be enhanced with information from one or more other modalities, exactly as it happens in the human brain [9].

The reconstruction algorithm is based on the pipeline shown in Fig. 2, which includes the following modules:

Fig. 2. Pipeline of the shape reconstruction algorithm: grey blocks are standard PCL methods, and blue blocks are software modules developed in this work.

Acquisition of the visual point cloud. The RGB-D camera captures the visual PC.

Pre-processing. The acquired PC is pre-processed to define a region of interest to be segmented.

Color-based segmentation. The visual PC is divided into clusters by a color-based segmentation, a standard PCL (Point Cloud Library) algorithm. Each cluster can represent either a piece of cable or an occluding object because the background has been previously removed.

Downsampling. This step is used to reduce the point density and minimize the computational complexity of the subsequent steps. The algorithm defines a grid within the area occupied by the cluster by selecting the number of cells along the x direction as the size of the area along x divided by a certain distance d_m . The number of cells along the y direction is selected likewise. The points inside each cell of the grid are replaced by their centroid.

Post-processing. This operation is necessary because each downsampled PC (cluster) may have some points too close to each other and, in turn, can generate a non-smooth curve after the spline interpolation. The algorithm is simple: when the Euclidean distance between two points of the PC is under a certain threshold t_P they are replaced by the midpoint.

Check occlusion. The PC after the post-processing could be either a cable part or an occluding object. To make the decision, the cluster points are sorted according to an algorithm that tries to reorder the points along the cable direction. If the cluster is a cable, only a few points are removed; whereas, if the cluster is an occluding object the sorting algorithm excludes almost all points of the PC. The algorithm starts from an arbitrary point and selects all the neighbouring points (with a given threshold t_N); then, it computes the angles among all the vectors starting from the initial point and ending in all its neighbours. The initial sorting direction is defined as the one with the smallest angle. The sorting phase starts by finding the neighbours of the second point found above and computes the angles among all the vectors again from this point to the neighbours. A new point is added to the sorted list if the corresponding angle is below a given threshold t_α , hence some

Fig. 3. Experimental setup: cable with a straight line (left) and spiral-like (right) shape.

points could be removed. This procedure leads to a sorted PC that might cover only part of the cable since the sorting phase terminates with one of the two cable ends, thus disregarding the cable portion until its second end. This problem can be solved by launching a second sorting phase on the original PC starting from the last two points of the previously sorted PC. Each cluster with significantly fewer points than the initial ones is recognized as an occluding object and is forwarded to the module performing the tactile exploration.

Acquisition of the tactile point cloud. The input cluster defines a region the robot has to explore with the tactile sensor. The exploration consists in touching with the tactile pad a set of points inside this region. The tactile data are usefully interpreted to decide if the robot is touching the support table or the cable at each point. The norm of the matrix containing the Hessian matrix norms of the tactile map is used as a metric to discriminate between a flat contact surface and a cable. If the metric exceeds a threshold t_H , the position of the centroid of the tactile map, at which the contact has been detected, is used to define the coordinates of a point of the tactile PC.

Euclidean distance-based segmentation. The acquired tactile PC might contain separate cable parts, easily identified through a standard Euclidean distance-based segmentation. The resulting clusters can now be processed by the same pipeline followed by the visual PCs.

Merging. This module concatenates the different clusters identified as cable parts to obtain a unique PC.

Interpolation. The points obtained by merging visual and tactile PCs are here interpolated by a B-spline [10]. The interpolation requires the points to be sorted along the direction of the curve describing the cable shape. To this aim, the same sorting algorithm used in the Check occlusion step is adopted. Once sorted, the points are interpolated by the B-spline, which models the reconstructed cable shape.

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF THE CABLE RECONSTRUCTION ALGORITHM

d_m [mm]	t_P [mm]	t_H [mm]	t_N [mm]	t_α [rad]
15	13	1.15	60	1

Fig. 4. First experiment: Visual and tactile PCs of the cable with a straight line shape interpolated by a spline.

Fig. 5. Second experiment: Visual and tactile PCs of the cable with a spiral-like shape interpolated by a spline.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents two experimental case studies to show how the results, even if preliminary, of the cable reconstruction, are satisfactory not only when the cable has a straight shape but also in more challenging configurations, like spiral-like shapes. Tab. I reports the parameters used in the algorithm.

The experimental setup (see Fig. 3-left) includes a 7-axis Yaskawa Motoman SIA5F robot equipped with an eye-in-hand Intel Realsense D410i RGB-D camera and a SUNTouch tactile[11] sensor. A blue cable is laid out on a white support surface with an almost straight line shape in the left picture and a spiral-like shape in the right one. In both cases, the cable is partially occluded by a piece of black fabric.

The results of the shape reconstruction in the first case (straight line shape) are reported in Fig. 4. The blue dots constitute the visual PC and it does not contain the part of the cable covered by the fabric. Therefore, the check occlusion step starts a tactile exploration and the resulting PC is shown with red dots. The resulting merged PC is then interpolated and the spline shown with a green line reconstructs the cable shape with a satisfactory quality.

The proposed perception algorithm is applied to a second case study, where the cable has a spiral-like shape again partially occluded by a piece of fabric (see Fig. 3-right).

The blue dots in Fig. 5 show the visual PCs obtained after the downsampling step. It is evident how they do not contain

the two parts of the cable covered by the portion of fabric, hence the check occlusion phase asks the robot to explore with the tactile sensor the area covered by the fabric autonomously detected in this step. The obtained tactile PC is shown with red dots, corresponding to the two portions of cables occluded by the fabric. The complete PC is then interpolated by a spline shown with the green line. Also in this more challenging case, where there are separate occluded parts of the cable, the robot successfully reconstructs the whole cable shape.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The work presented the first results of a new algorithm for cross-modal visuo-tactile perception of DLOs. The method can reconstruct the shape of a cable, under a few simplifying assumptions, even in the presence of severe occlusions. Future research efforts will be devoted to optimising the various algorithms, especially those dedicated to classifying portions of cable and occluded parts. The algorithm will also be extended to possible entanglements of the cable and multiple cables. The refined method will be the base of a more general framework of cross-modal learning for DLO manipulation.

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